

Ethical Technology Adoption in Public Administrations

Ensuring trustworthy digital public services across Europe

Key insights

For Public Administrations and policymakers

- **Code of Conduct and Standard Governance Procedures**
Adopt a specific code of conduct and put in place standard procedures to deal with technology adoption, risk monitoring and mitigation.
- **Proactive Risk Management and Continuous Monitoring**
Implement robust and tailored risk assessment mechanisms since the design phase of the adoption or development process. Regular ethical assessments detect and mitigate deviations from established standards promptly, ensuring ethical, social and legal compliance.
- **Upskilling Public Servants**
The workforce should be familiar with emerging technology and able to oversee ethics. This can be achieved through dedicated hands-on training programmes.
- **Citizens' Engagement**
Involve citizens when adopting and assessing technologies that affect public services. Collecting feedback strengthens trust and legitimacy in public institutions and technology.
- **Legal Alignment and Consultations**
Establish regular consultations with the legal unit. This ensures alignment with both legal and ethical standards which is crucial considering the evolving EU legal framework on emerging technology.

Investment Priorities at European level

ETAPAS Policy Brief #3

Ethical Technology Adoption in Public Administrations: Ensuring trustworthy digital public services across Europe.

ABSTRACT

The issue at hand revolves around the increasing adoption of Disruptive Technologies (DTs) in European Public Administrations (PAs), where cutting-edge technologies like Big Data, AI and Robotics are reshaping how services are delivered. While these technologies hold the potential for efficiency gains and cost savings, they raise significant ethical and social concerns. The European Union has been actively working on a legal framework to regulate AI and emerging technologies, but changes are frequent, causing uncertainty for adopting organizations. Equipping PAs with digital skills and ethics expertise is a pressing need.

For Public Administrations and citizens, responsible adoption of DTs is crucial to avoid potential harm, legal implications, and governance risks. A notable case in the Netherlands highlights the dangers of discriminatory biases in algorithms. On the positive side, ethical technology adoption promises risk reduction, streamlined procedures, improved service delivery, and strengthened trust in public institutions.

To address these challenges, policymakers should focus on analysing their context, building multidisciplinary teams, putting in place standardized governance procedures involving risk assessment and mitigation and legal consultations, adopting code of conducts, providing training programs to public servants and engaging citizens.

At the European level, investment priorities should be directed towards R&D funding for ethical DT adoption, digital skills training for public servants, simplifying innovation procurement, enabling AI Act compliance, creating public awareness on digital ethics, and supporting the development of ethical DT solutions in Europe. Additionally, fostering international collaboration on ethical tech research and deployment is crucial for establishing global standards and guidelines.

In conclusion, responsible adoption of Disruptive Technologies in European PAs is imperative to harness their benefits while safeguarding against potential risks and ethical concerns. Policymakers should focus on comprehensive approaches and targeted investments to ensure a trustworthy and ethical digital transformation.

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1. WHAT'S THE ISSUE?

Public Administrations (PAs) across Europe are in the midst of a transformative shift, actively embracing emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Robotics, Big Data, and the Internet of Things (IoT) to modernize and improve public service delivery. These technologies offer the potential for increased efficiency, cost savings, and more responsive services. However, this rapid adoption of Disruptive Technologies (DTs) has brought forth significant ethical and social concerns.

Increasing Adoption of Disruptive Technologies in European Public Administration

EU AI investment

Figure 1 - EU AI investment 2019-2025

European DT adoption rates have been increasing in recent years. AI, and in particular generative AI, adoption rates have grown the faster. The contribution of the Public Sector (PS) to technology investments is quite substantial, e.g., the **public sector's share** of EU AI investment accounted to **42% of EU AI investments** already in 2018¹.

Public services' digitalisation is rising fast, as is the share of European PAs adopting DTs to this end. Also on the user side the trend is clear: the number of e-Government users out of the total internet users increased from the 65% to the 75% in the last year².

Several European countries and local governments have initiated projects to integrate AI, Big Data, Robotics and other DT solutions, aiming to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of public service delivery.

According to the most recent literature³, more than a third of AI cases in PAs are implemented and used in daily operations, indicating a **shift beyond mere pilot stages**. The majority of AI initiatives are launched at the national level, indicating that AI development is primarily driven by national governments.

Figure 2 - AI adoption across EU PA sectors

However, **shortfalls** still emerge in terms of **citizen engagement** in the design of DT-based services and **digital literacy among public servants** dealing with DT systems. Moreover, the disruptive potential of Big Data, AI and Robotics within public services delivery has yet to materialize into tangible, large-scale projects with broad-reaching impacts on public affairs. This is also due to the difficulties in **foreseeing the large-scale impacts** of adopting disruptive technologies in PAs, especially in the absence of **structured means to manage the associated social, legal and ethical risks** from the design phase of the solutions through to operation.

¹ Sources: Figure 1: Daniel Nepelski and Maciej Sobolewski, Estimating investments in General Purpose Technologies. The case of AI Investments in Europe, EUR 30072 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2020, ISBN 978-92-76-10233-5, doi:10.2760/506947, JRC118953; Figure 2: AI-X - AI Public Services Explorer - AI Watch European Union (<https://ai-watch.github.io/AI-watch-T6-X/chart/>).

² <https://digital-decade-desi.digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/datasets/desi/charts>

³ Tangi, Luca, Colin Van Noordt, Marco Combetto, Dietmar Gattwinkel and Francesco Pignatelli. AI Watch. European landscape on the use of Artificial Intelligence by the Public Sector (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2022).

Evolving Legal Framework

Figure 3 - European legal framework on AI⁶

The European Union has been highly committed in recent years in regulating the AI market and promoting ethical AI and technology adoption. Starting from the Coordinated Plan, the White Paper, the AI HLEG Guidelines up to the recent AI Act Proposal, **the European legal framework for AI is taking shape**. Within this effort the Digital services, Digital Market and Data Governance Acts are clarifying the legal framework more broadly around digital services. Also other emerging technologies are being regulated within EU e.g., the Markets in Crypto-Assets Regulation⁴ is defining rules for blockchain-based crypto assets and there is a proposal for a New Machinery Regulation⁵ directly addressing robots and manufacturing 3D-printers.

Nevertheless, **changes** in this regard **are frequent** and partly **difficult to predict, bringing uncertainty** to organisation that would like to adopt AI solutions or other emerging technologies, especially in the Public Sector. Similarly at national level many European Member States adopted **national strategies** to deal with AI and updated them in a matter of months⁷. Many national strategies emphasize stimulating the local GovTech ecosystem, assisting start-ups and other companies to develop AI for government use, together with the need for general training for most public servants, as well as for more specialized training to allow in-house DT development⁸.

To facilitate legal certainty behind PA technology adoption, ETAPAS provides an analysis of the European legal framework⁹ and recommends an iterative and interactive legal assessment process with the organisations' legal department¹⁰.

Digital and Digital Ethics Skills Gaps

One of the most pressing challenges lies in the lack of technology skills and digital ethics expertise within European PAs. Examining technological skills at the European level, it is projected that an additional 1.7 million employees (constituting 5.3 percent of the current 32 million public-sector employees in EU-28 countries) possessing digital skills will be required across the PS in the EU-28 in the upcoming years¹¹.

Figure 4 - ETAPAS - EU Legal Framework on DTs

⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020PC0593>

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/45508>

⁶ Pellegrino, M., Galasso, G., Mancini, S., Messina, T., Mumeni Urbani, I, Codagnone, J.A. (2022) The AI Act: help or hindrance for SMEs? An analysis of the cost of compliance with the AI Act for SMEs. Available at: https://www.intelleraconsulting.com/documents/42559/59109/Alactpaper_v16_singola_web.pdf/21ea39c2-7b26-7115-5266-a49e8875e7be?t=1668448362037

⁷ Jorge Ricart et al., 2022

⁸ Tangi, Luca, Colin Van Noordt, Marco Combetto, Dietmar Gattwinkel and Francesco Pignatelli. AI Watch. European landscape on the use of Artificial Intelligence by the Public Sector (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2022).

⁹ See ETAPAS Legal Implications of the use Of DTs <https://www.etapasproject.eu/resources/deliverables/>

¹⁰ See ETAPAS Guidelines to legal assessment within the ETAPAS Governance Model <https://www.etapasproject.eu/resources/deliverables/>

¹¹ Chinn, D., Hieronimus, S., Kirchherr, J., and Klier, J. (2020) The future is now: Closing the skills gap in Europe's public sector.

Available at <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/public-sector/our-insights/the-future-is-now-closing-the-skills-gap-in-europes-public-sector#/>

THE AI AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION COMPETENCY FRAMEWORK

01. DIGITAL PLANNING AND DESIGN

COMPETENCY AREAS AND SKILLS

- PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION AND SOLUTIONS**
Identify problems in which digital technology might be part of the solution.
- SYSTEMS THINKING**
Understand how problems are connected in systems.
- STRATEGIC FORESIGHT**
Anticipate problems and unexpected circumstances.
- AGILE STRATEGY**
Ability to plan initiatives while remaining flexible and adapting to unexpected circumstances.

02. DATA USE AND GOVERNANCE

COMPETENCY AREAS AND SKILLS

- DIGITAL LITERACY**
Understand emerging digital technology and its applications.
- DATA-DRIVEN DECISION-MAKING**
Mine, analyze and use data in the decisionmaking process of public policies.
- OPEN DATA AND OPEN GOVERNMENT**
Capacity to effectively create and use open data.
- PRIVACY AND SECURITY**
Knowledge of potential breaches and how can they affect government and society.
- LEGAL, REGULATORY AND ETHICAL FRAMEWORKS**
Capacity to adapt and change existing legislation to emerging technologies. If needed, to create tech-friendly legislation.
- AI FUNDAMENTALS**
Understand AI systems to a basic level.

03. DIGITAL MANAGEMENT AND EXECUTION

COMPETENCY AREAS AND SKILLS

- PEOPLE-CENTRICITY**
Ability to take into high consideration the user experience and needs on digital public policies and technologies.
- ITERATION**
Learn and accept mistakes as part of the digital project cycle.
- AGILE EXECUTION**
Capacity to formulate technical, logistic and strategic requirements for public digital projects and execute them.
- DIGITAL LEADERSHIP**
Ability to develop a vision for digital.

Figure 5 - OECD Competency Framework

Nevertheless, this issue is felt at a global level, indeed digital transformation has become an essential tool for public sector organizations to address complex problems ranging from environmental degradation to global warming and socioeconomic inequalities. Addressing this need, the OECD has published a competency framework for civil servants on AI and digital transformation to provide guidance to develop curricula and action plans and strategies on digital competencies¹².

On top of this, specific digital ethics skills are required to grant trustworthy digital public services and a sound ethical oversight of the digital transformation processes. The urgency to comply with the AI Act requirements and other EU regulations and guidelines, as well as with societal expectations, increase the need for PAs to rely on in-house trained professionals to oversee the adoption of digital technologies, ensuring legal, ethical and social compliance.

Recently more and more PAs are undertaking initiatives to try to fill in the digital ethics skills gap in the PS. Main policy initiatives regarded stimulating awareness, improving data access and quality, improving internal capacity through training and change management, as well as spreading ethical and legal AI guidelines throughout the organisations¹³.

2. WHY IS THIS IMPORTANT FOR PUBLIC ADMINISTRATIONS AND CITIZENS?

The adoption of disruptive technologies in the PS holds great promise but comes with a **range of risks**. According to ETAPAS extensive research and risk mapping¹⁴, these include potential physical and psychological harm in direct user interactions, legal implications such as liability and law infringement, and governance risks due to weak oversight and non-standardized procedures. Additionally, there are concerns regarding the exacerbation of inequalities and discriminations, potential errors and misuse, as well as security and data protection risks. Lastly, issues of unsustainable use and workplace implications, such as job displacement and the need for new skills, require careful management.

Addressing these risks calls for a comprehensive approach integrating robust governance, ethical guidelines, and a solid legal framework.

Figure 6 - Overview of PS risks in adopting DTs solutions

¹² UNESCO (2022). AI and Digital Transformation Competencies for Civil Servants.

<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000383325>

¹³ Tangi L., van Noordt C., Combetto M., Gattwinkel D., Pignatelli F., AI Watch. European Landscape on the Use of Artificial Intelligence by the Public Sector, EUR 31088 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-53058-9, doi:10.2760/39336, JRC129301.

¹⁴ See ETAPAS Report on potential risks of DTs in public administration <https://www.etapasproject.eu/resources/deliverables/>

An **exemplar case** of the occurrence of some of the mentioned risks could be represented by the **welfare algorithm used in Netherlands** from 2013 to 2021 and that contributed to wrongly accuse about 26,000 innocent families of social benefits fraud due to discriminatory biases. The algorithm was considering factors like living situation, gender, and familial relationships, leading to biased outcomes and disproportionately accusing black peoples. Forced to pay back debts they were not responsible for, many families were pushed to the brick of financial collapse and others were left with lasting mental health issues. In addition to the discriminatory biases, the algorithm was rising accountability, security, transparency and explainability concerns. Due to this, in 2021 the use of the algorithm was suspended and subjected to an external ethical investigation and verification that confirmed its biases and poor coordination¹⁵.

Benefits of Ethical Technology Adoption

On the other hand, the benefits of adopting emerging technologies in an ethical way are outstanding:

- **Risk Reduction and Mitigation** – The implementation of ethical risk governance substantially diminishes the likelihood of costly errors, regulatory violations, and the accompanying public backlash. This directly translates into fiscal savings and heightened reputational protection for PAs.
- **Streamlined Adoption and Monitoring Procedures** - Ethical guidelines simplify and streamline the adoption and continuous monitoring of DTs. This results in more efficient processes, allowing for resource allocation optimization.
- **Fostering an Ethical Culture** - Committing to digital ethics within PAs not only ensures responsible technology use but also fosters an organizational culture where ethics are at the forefront of decision-making. This cultural shift has far-reaching implications for public trust and accountability.
- **Improving Public Service Delivery** - Emerging technologies can greatly improve the efficiency and effectiveness of public services when adopted/developed with a sound ethical, social and legal governance.
- **Strengthening Trust in Public Institutions** - Ethical technology adoption builds and sustains trust with citizens and end-users. Trust is the bedrock of effective governance, and its preservation is paramount for PAs to fulfill their mandates effectively and maintain legitimacy.

An example of these benefits is offered by the 4 ETAPAS use cases, that can testify how the ethical adoption of DTs in the public sector can lead to:

Figure 7 - Example benefits from ethical adoption

¹⁵ <https://incidentdatabase.ai/cite/101/#r1575>

3. WHAT SHOULD POLICYMAKERS DO?

ETAPAS offers a comprehensive approach and toolkit to address the ethical challenges posed by DT adoption in PA. ETAPAS is a multifaceted framework that seamlessly integrates technological solutions, governance structures, and educational initiatives to promote responsible technology adoption. The following recommendations for European Policy Makers are derived from the ETAPAS research and experience of co-design and testing with European PAs.

- Context analysis:** Analysing the initial context, including sector and type of organisation, social expectations, etc. is the best way to tailor the ethical assessment process starting from the design phase or from the selection of the solution to be adopted¹⁶.
- Multidisciplinary Teams:** To effectively address complex ethical issues, PAs should establish multidisciplinary teams that encompass a diverse range of expertise. This includes ethicists, technologists, legal experts, and domain specialists who can collaboratively tackle multifaceted ethical dilemmas and ensure holistic ethical assessments.
- Risk Assessment, Mitigation and Monitoring:** Policymakers should institute robust risk assessment and continuous monitoring mechanisms to identify and address ethical concerns proactively. Regular ethical assessments are critical for detecting deviations from established ethical standards and implementing corrective measures promptly¹⁷.
- Standardized Governance Procedures:** Policymakers should actively encourage the development and implementation of standardized procedures for technology adoption, ensuring ethical compliance at every stage of the adoption process. These standardized procedures should be adaptable to various technologies, simple to understand and follow, as well as easy to integrate with existing bureaucratic procedures, allowing for a cohesive approach to ethical compliance¹⁸.
- Code of Conduct Adoption:** Policymakers should develop and adopt throughout the organisation a clear and comprehensive code of conduct for technology adoption and ethical use. This code should articulate the fundamental principles that govern the ethical adoption and use of DTs within the organisation and its widespread dissemination among public servants should be ensured¹⁹.
- Public Servants Training Programs:** Policymakers must take proactive steps to develop and provide extensive training programs aimed at equipping PA staff with the necessary skills to navigate the intricate landscape of digital ethics. These training programs should encompass a broad spectrum of topics, including bias mitigation, transparency, accountability, and trustworthy AI.
- Legal Unit Consultation:** Policymakers should emphasize the importance of establishing regular consultations with the legal unit to ensure alignment with both legal and ethical standards. This ongoing consultation process not only guarantees that adopted technologies are ethically sound but also legally compliant, considering that the EU legal framework on emerging technology is in constant evolution.
- Citizens Engagement:** Citizen engagement is about involving people directly in the decisions that affect their daily lives. On one hand, citizens are the final users of many digital public services, on the other they are the source of PA legitimacy. This is way it is crucial to engage them, collecting feedback and requirements throughout the development or adoption process. This will also allow to strengthen the trust relationship of citizens towards PA and technology.

¹⁶ See the ETAPAS Validation method and guidelines

¹⁷ See the ETAPAS Responsible DT Indicators and metrics <https://www.etapasproject.eu/resources/deliverables/> and the ETAPAS Governance Platform

¹⁸ See the ETAPAS Governance Model <https://www.etapasproject.eu/resources/deliverables/>

¹⁹ See the ETAPAS Code of Conduct for DT adoption in the PS <https://www.etapasproject.eu/resources/deliverables/>

4. WHAT ARE THE INVESTMENT PRIORITIES AT EUROPEAN LEVEL?

To facilitate ethical DT adoption in PAs and ensure trustworthy digital public services in Europe, the European Commission (EC) should consider the following **investment priorities for the period 2024-2030** based on the ETAPAS research results.

1. Facilitating trustworthy DT adoption in PA and increasing maturity of DT-based projects in the PS

- a) R&D funding for Ethical DT Adoption in PAs
- b) Innovation funding for Trustworthy Digital Services Development
- c) Innovation funding for Trustworthy DT Solutions Deployment by Central and Local PAs

Dedicated funds for R&D and Innovation programs focused on the ethical adoption and trustworthy development of DTs in PAs could help improve public service delivery for citizens and ensure a trustworthy DT adoption. These funds should support projects that aim to address ethical concerns from the very inception of technology development, ensuring ethical considerations are integrated from the outset and established as standard procedures. Also, [sustainability and inclusiveness-oriented DT projects should be prioritised](#). AI and DTs adoption in the public sector is not yet very mature, therefore investments would aim to fund adoption or take it [from pilot status to operations](#). This approach goes in the direction of helping PAs grasp the nuances and begin the process of compliance with the [new regulatory requirements](#) and in particular those of the AI Act.

2. Increasing digital and digital-ethics skills of public servants across EU through dedicated training programmes

- a) General training programmes for all public servants aimed at rising digital skills
- b) Specific upskilling programmes for PAs that have recently adopted or plan to adopt DT solutions
- c) Training programmes targeting the innovation departments of PAs on AI and digital ethics oversight

Specific training programmes on ethical DT adoption for public servants and managers of European PAs should be financed and harmonized. Improved digital competences in civil servants mean better management of technology and digitalization in PA, with better services offered and consequently strengthen citizens trust in public institutions. Core topics should embrace [privacy, transparency, cybersecurity, assessment methods and practices, as well as the relevant EU legal framework](#). ETAPAS experience and research has shown that learning-by-doing and hand-on training is much more effective in this context. Accordingly, these training programmes should include a practical part and be tailored to the PA context. Furthermore, specific tools and training for continuous ethical and legal assessment are needed (See investment priority n. 4).

3. Simplifying and encouraging Innovation Procurement and Public-Private Partnerships

- a) Simplifying bureaucratic procedures for ethical technology adoption in PA and harmonizing innovation procurement procedures in Europe
- b) Creating mechanisms to bring together and certify SMEs, startups, GovTech companies that develop trustworthy DT solutions for the PS
- c) Funding for the development of public-private partnerships for the ethical development of DT solutions

When we asked PAs what the main obstacles to innovation were, they answered poor digital skills (see investment priority 2) and long bureaucratic procedures to be accommodated also in innovation processes. Bureaucratic procedures make it more complex and slower for the PS to innovate, making it less competitive in the digital market. In partnerships with the private sector, the PS demands that the highest ethical standards are met. Accordingly, encouraging collaborations between the public and private sectors could help promoting the responsible adoption of DTs. The EC should establish frameworks that facilitate such partnerships, with a specific focus on [ethical guidelines, standards and best practices](#). For instance, support can be provided to PAs in writing specifications for the procurement of AI solutions²⁰ in line with the AI Act and standard public procurement templates and contract clauses can be made available through handbooks. In addition, it is important to ensure that tender requirements are clear and do not cut out start-ups and SMEs. Specific channels should be provided for PAs to meet and engage innovative SMEs and startups that ensure ethical and legal compliance. This kind of structured collaboration could enable a holistic approach to ethical technology adoption in EU, ensuring that the meteoric spread of certain DTs, e.g., generative AI recently, does not take place at the expense of human rights and security but is handled ethically and trustworthily, especially in the PS.

²⁰ In line with EU and OECD standards: <https://public-buyers-community.ec.europa.eu/communities/procurement-ai/news/new-version-procurement-clauses-ai-available-supporting-responsible>

4. Enabling AI Act compliance and Ethical Assessment of DT solutions in the PS

a) Development and provision of approaches and tools to simplify AI Act compliance and ethical assessment of DT solutions development or adoption in the public sector

Substantial investments are needed for the dissemination and wide implementation of comprehensive methodologies and tools for conducting ethical assessment of DT solutions in PA (e.g. ETAPAS approach). In order to meet the requirements of the AI Act and other regulations, PAs need practical tools to help them. These tools must be *co-developed and tested with the PAs* to meet their context, needs and be effectively useful, just as was done in the ETAPAS project. Furthermore, as the ETAPAS research showed, these tools must be used in a structured manner, throughout the entire technology adoption or development process and must be accompanied by specific, practical training (see investment priority 2). Finally, these assessments should be tailored to specific technologies and sectors, and should engage experts, stakeholders, and the public to gather diverse perspectives, ensuring a well-rounded evaluation.

5. Creating Public Awareness on AI and digital ethics and the benefits of DT adoption in public services

a) Digital upskilling programmes for residents, including ethical aspects

b) Public awareness campaigns on risk and benefits of AI and DTs adoption in public services

Substantial resources should be allocated to *public awareness campaigns and educational initiatives* that specifically focus on the ethical implications of DTs. These initiatives should aim to enhance digital literacy among EU residents and promote responsible technology use. A well-informed public plays a vital role in *holding both PAs and private entities accountable*. Furthermore, according to ETAPAS experience, this effort is complementary to that of facilitating ethical DT adoption within the PS. An educated public that grasps the benefits of digital and DT-based public services, increases its trust in technology and PA if it sees trustworthy adoption practices within the public sector. An ethical assessment and adoption process should always involve *residents' engagement* both through the collection of feedback and the dissemination of awareness. Their involvement will make the DT-based public service more responsive to their needs and thus more effective, just as it will make the ethical assessment more comprehensive and effective.

6. Developing market-leading European DT solutions ethical by design

a) Ethical Investment Funds to promote innovative ethical DT solutions development made in EU

The market demands for innovative European technology solutions able to rival the tech giants from the rest of the world, ethical by design and supporting ethical adoption. Development and market entry costs are heavy to bear for organisations. To this end, the EC should actively support the creation of investment funds or initiatives that prioritize ethical development and responsible use of DTs in Europe. This would ensure that financial resources are channeled towards endeavors that *align with ethical standards and best practices*. Further, a fund promoting the development of European, ethical and trustworthy technological solutions would benefit both the private and public sectors, as well as final users in EU.

7. Fostering International Collaboration on ethical tech research and deployment

a) Fostering joint initiatives on ethical AI and DTs requirements and standards

b) Knowledge exchanges about ethical AI and DTs development and adoption best practices

Engaging in international collaborations and information sharing to establish global standards and guidelines for the ethical adoption of DTs in PA has an outstanding importance. The EU should actively collaborate with international organizations, as happened with UNESCO for the global standard on AI ethics²¹, as well as with other countries to address common challenges and *promote responsible practices on a global scale*. International harmonization is critical, considering the transnational nature of technology and its ethical implications.

²¹ UNESCO produced the first-ever global standard on AI ethics – the 'Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence' in November 2021 <https://www.unesco.org/en/artificial-intelligence/recommendation-ethics>. UNESCO and the EC have signed in June 2023 an agreement to accelerate global implementation of the UNESCO Recommendation on the ethics of artificial intelligence by the 193 Member States of the Organization. A budget of €4 million will be dedicated to supporting the least developed countries in the establishment of their national legislation <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/artificial-intelligence-partnership-between-unesco-and-eu-speed-implementation-ethical-rules>.

INVESTMENT PRIORITIES AT EUROPEAN LEVEL

- 1. FACILITATING TRUSTWORTHY DT ADOPTION IN PA AND INCREASING MATURITY OF DT-BASED PROJECTS IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR**

 - a) R&D funding for Ethical DT Adoption in PAs
 - b) Innovation funding for Trustworthy Digital Services Development
 - c) Innovation funding for Trustworthy DT Solutions Deployment by Central and Local PAs
- 2. INCREASING DIGITAL AND DIGITAL-ETHICS SKILLS OF PUBLIC SERVANTS ACROSS EU THROUGH DEDICATED TRAINING PROGRAMMES**

 - a) General training programmes for all public servants
 - b) Specific upskilling programmes for PAs that have recently adopted or plan to adopt DT solutions
 - c) Training programmes targeting the innovation departments of PAs on AI and digital ethics oversight
- 3. SIMPLIFYING AND ENCOURAGING INNOVATION PROCUREMENT AND PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS**

 - a) Simplifying bureaucratic procedures for adopting trustworthy DT solutions and harmonizing innovation procurement procedures in Europe
 - b) Bring together and certify SMEs, startups, GovTech companies that develop trustworthy DT solutions for the PS
 - c) Funding for the development of public-private partnerships for the ethical development of DT solutions
- 4. ENABLING AI ACT COMPLIANCE AND ETHICAL ASSESSMENT OF DT SOLUTIONS IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR**

 - a) Development and provision of approaches and tools to simplify AI Act compliance and ethical assessment of DT solutions development or adoption in the public sector
- 5. CREATING PUBLIC AWARENESS ON AI AND DIGITAL ETHICS AND THE BENEFITS OF DT ADOPTION IN PUBLIC SERVICES**

 - a) Digital upskilling programmes for residents, including ethical aspects
 - b) Public awareness campaigns on risk and benefits of AI and DTs adoption in public services
- 6. DEVELOPING MARKET-LEADING EUROPEAN DT SOLUTIONS ETHICAL BY DESIGN**

 - a) Ethical Investment Funds to promote innovative ethical DT solutions development made in EU
- 7. FOSTERING INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION ON ETHICAL TECH RESEARCH AND DEPLOYMENT**

 - a) Fostering joint initiatives on ethical AI and DTs requirements and standards
 - b) Knowledge exchanges about ethical AI and DTs development and adoption best practices

5. CLOSING REMARKS

As we navigate this digital frontier, it is paramount to strike a delicate balance between innovation and ethics. The lessons learned from cases like the welfare algorithm in the Netherlands serve as stark reminders of the consequences of overlooking ethical dimensions. Discriminatory biases, legal ramifications, and governance risks can arise if not managed conscientiously.

Yet, the potential benefits of responsible DT adoption in the public sector are equally profound. They encompass risk reduction, streamlined procedures, improved service delivery, and, most importantly, strengthened trust in public institutions. Through ethical governance, we have the power to shape a future where technology serves as an ally, not an adversary.

Policymakers play a pivotal role in charting this course. By standardizing governance procedures, adopting codes of conducts and performing continuous risk assessment, they pave the way for a future where ethics are woven into the fabric of technological progress.

At the European level, strategic investments are crucial. R&D funding for ethical DT adoption, digital skills training, and simplifying innovation procurement are all cornerstones of a future-ready public sector. Compliance with the AI Act, public awareness campaigns, and the development of market-leading European DT solutions underscore the commitment to ethical progress. Furthermore, international collaboration is indispensable. By joining forces, we can establish global standards that ensure ethical tech adoption resonates across borders.

In conclusion, the journey toward a trustworthy and ethical digital transformation is one that requires steadfast dedication and concerted effort. Let us move forward with the knowledge that, by embracing ethics, we unlock the full potential of Disruptive Technologies in the service of European citizens and the public good.

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